

Characterization of microITIES modified with polyamides

Karolina Kowalewska^{a*}, Karolina Kwaczyński^a, Madjid Tarabet^b, Karolina Sobczak^a, Andrzej Leniart^a, Sławomira Skrzypek^a, Manuel Dossot^b, Gregoire Herzog^b, Łukasz Póltorak^{a*}

a. Electrochemistry@Soft Interfaces Team, Department of Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry, Faculty of Chemistry, University of Lodz, Tamka 12, 91-403 Lodz, Poland.

b. Université de Lorraine, CNRS, LCPME, 54000 Nancy, France

***Corresponding authors:** lukasz.poltorak@chemia.uni.lodz.pl

karolina.kowalewska@chemia.uni.lodz.pl

Abstract

In this work, we present the possibility to electrochemically assist and study interfacial polycondensation derived from the reactions between 1,6-diaminohexane or *p*-phenylenediamine used as the diamine (always initially present in the aqueous phase) and acyl chlorides in a form of 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride, terephthaloyl chloride or adipoyl chloride (present in the organic phase – 1,2-dichloroethane solution). Synthesized polyamides are formed at the polarized liquid – liquid interfaces (or the interface between two immiscible electrolyte solutions – ITIES) as a consequence of the partly protonated diamine transfer from the aqueous to the organic phase. In this respect, we have defined the aqueous phase pH assuring availability of the amine groups (-NH₂) for the reaction with the acyl chloride and protonated amine groups (-NH₃⁺) defining the electrochemical interfacial activity of chosen compounds. The possibility to electrochemically assist the interfacial formation of polyamides was first tested using the macroscopic ITIES. Formed polyamides were collected and analysed using scanning electron microscopy, energy dispersive x-ray spectroscopy and Raman spectroscopy. Next, we have employed the microscopic ITIES (microITIES) based system formed using fused silica microcapillaries. Cyclic voltammetry was employed for the polyamide modified microITIES assessment (evolution of molecular sieving properties using a model ion - tetramethylammonium cation).

Keywords: polyamides, interfacial polycondensation, polarized liquid – liquid interface, Kevlar, Nylon, acyl chlorides, diamine.

1. Introduction

Polyamides belong to the large group of polymers having an amide bond present in their structure. Polyamides can be divided into aliphatic (straight-chain), aromatic (aramids) and semi-aromatic (polyphthalamides). Aliphatic polyamides form straight chain monomers. Whenever two monomers, each containing an aromatic ring in its structure react, we obtain aramid. Polyphthalamides are formed as the result of the reaction between aromatic and aliphatic monomers. Polyamides hold valuable commercial importance. They have many industrial applications, primarily in the textile industry for the production of clothes, but are also a component of ropes, lines, toothbrushes or tights [1,2]. Polyamide based materials are also frequently applied in R&D laboratories due to the high resistivity to organic solvents. These class of materials is especially useful as membranes [3], but also find applications as adsorbents [4] or for labware fabrication [5]. One can obtain polyamides by interfacial polymerization derived from a reaction between compounds containing multiple amine and acid chloride groups [6]. The substrates are dissolved in the aqueous and the organic phases (based on their solubility) and react at the junction formed between two immiscible liquids to form a polyamide material. The interfacial deposit is formed until (i) one of the reactants is exhausted, or (ii) the compactness of the formed polymer inhibits the transfer of the reactants to the soft junction. The reaction can be also impeded by the proton formed upon amide bond formation. Very popular example of a polyamide derived from the interfacial polycondensation is Nylon-6.6 [7]. It can be obtained quickly, spontaneously and easily in a spectacular manner, known as the "nylon rope trick" [8]. Since the protons are formed as by-products of the reaction between amine and acyl chloride groups, the interfacial polycondensation can be electrochemically assisted at the polarized liquid – liquid interfaces (the presence of protons allows the protonation of the amine groups triggering the interfacial electrochemical activity of the concerned compounds) [9].

Electrochemistry at the Interface between Two Immiscible Electrolyte Solutions (ITIES) is a platform that when combined with electroanalytical techniques allows the study of interfacial phenomena under the influence of an applied potential difference [10]. ITIES-based

systems are defect-free and self-healing, take the shape of the container, and can be studied with all available electrochemical techniques. The intrinsic properties of the ITIES are frequently employed to study purely ion interfacial charge transfer, providing an alternative to solid electrodes [11]. Macroscopic ITIES can be studied in a classical electrochemical cell equipped with two Luggin capillaries. Usually, the volume of each phase (either aqueous or organic) equals to a few mL. In the vast majority of reports, the ITIES is formed between an aqueous phase (highly hydrophilic salt (e.g. NaCl, HCl, LiCl) dissolved in water) and an organic phase (hydrophobic salt (e.g. bistrisphenylphosphoranyldiene tetrakis(4-chlorophenyldiene)borate) dissolved in a solvent like 1,2-dichloroethane, α,α,α -trifluorotoluene) [12–14]. A lot of attention is also given to miniaturize polarized liquid – liquid interfaces to ensure greater stability of the soft junction (aided by the employed supports with predesigned surface wettability/capillary forces) and allow the reduction in consumption of toxic chemicals (and chemicals in general) [15]. The liquid-liquid interface downscaling can be achieved with the supports made of polymer [16], silicon [17,18], or fiberglass membranes [19]. MicroITIES systems are also created by using glass tubes, or single/double barrel capillaries with a dimensionality ranging from few tens of nm to a few tens of μm [20,21]/ In this work, the microITIES was formed by placing a short piece of silica microcapillary tubing having 25 μm in diameter into a micropipette tip, further secure via heat treatment [22]. Resulting platforms allowed for the rapid fabrication that was beneficial for the microITIES modification with the polyamide material.

New properties of polarized liquid – liquid interfaces can be obtained by means of different materials placement at the soft junction. *In situ*-based modification methodology can be followed by (i) interfacial ion transfer, (ii) interfacial electron transfer, (iii) spontaneous adsorption to the interfacial region or (iv) interfacial polycondensation. An example of the interfacial deposition assisted by the ion transfer reaction of a surfactant molecules initially dissolved in the organic phase to the aqueous phase containing silanol species may lead to the electrochemically controlled synthesis of silica [23,24]. Moreover, the polarized liquid – liquid interfaces can be modified with metallic nanoparticles, which are formed as a result of interfacial electron transfer (e.g. from electron donor dissolved in the organic phase, to the aqueous reservoir of metallic NPs precursors) [25–28]. Examples cover the electrochemically controlled synthesis of Pd nanoparticles using an alumina membrane as a support [29], synthesis of gold nanofilm [27,30], or silver nanoparticles [31] at the ITIES. Several elegant

papers by Cunnane's team describe the interfacial formation of methyl and phenyl – pyrrole oligomers [32] and electropolymerization of 2,2':5',2''-terthiophene [33], the polymeric materials was controlled by interfacial electron transfer. Recent works discuss the formation of electrosynthesized poly(2,5-dimercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazole) films [34] or poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) thin films (the latter displaying exceptional biocompatibility) [35] at the polarized water- α,α,α -trifluorotoluene. Interfacial polycondensation defines a vast amount of growth polymerization reactions originating from a reaction between two or more monomers separated based on their solubility in the contacted immiscible phases. Vast amount of reactions can be rediscovered at the ITIES, especially when charged/ionisable function groups can be found within the structure of involved monomers. Recently we have shown, that polyamide interfacial polycondensation can be studied and assisted at the ITIES by the electrochemical control leading to a simple methodology allowing the LLI modification [9,25].

In this work, the electrochemically controlled synthesis of different polyamide materials was carried out. We modified ITIES with the polyamide films derived from the reaction between 1,6-diaminohexane or *p*-phenylenediamine used as the diamine (always initially present in the aqueous phase) and acyl chlorides in a form of 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride, terephthaloyl chloride or adipoyl chloride (present in the organic phase – 1,2-dichloroethane solution). Selected chemical species are popular monomers used for different polyamides formation, and hence, were also chosen to be studied at the ITIES. Polymers were formed at the macroscopic and miniaturized ITIES. Cyclic voltammetry was employed to assist the deposition process and to characterize modified ITIES permeability to ionic species. The materials extracted from ITIES were characterized using Raman spectroscopy and SEM – EDX.

2. Methods and materials

2.1. Chemicals

Sodium chloride (NaCl, $\geq 99,5\%$, Fisher Chemicals), acetic acid (CH_3COOH , 99.5 – 99.9%, POCh), phosphoric acid (H_3PO_4 , 80%, for analysis, ChemPur), boric acid (H_3BO_3 , for analysis, ChemPur) were used to prepare the Britton – Robinson buffer. Sodium hydroxide (NaOH, for analysis, POCh) were used to prepare 1M solution that were further employed for pH adjustment. Demineralized water (Hydrolab®) was used in all cases to prepare the aqueous solutions. The organic phase was hydrophobic salt ($\text{BTTPPA}^+\text{TPBCl}^-$) dissolved in 1,2 – dichloroethane (1,2-DCE, for analysis, POCh). The organic phase electrolyte $\text{BTTPPA}^+\text{TPBCl}^-$

(Bis(triphenylphosphoranylidene)ammonium tetrakis(4-chlorophenylborate)) was synthesized using bis(triphenylphosphoranylidene)ammonium chloride (BTPPA⁺Cl⁻, 97%, Sigma-Aldrich) and potassium tetrakis(4-chlorophenyl) (KTPB⁺Cl⁻, ≥98%, Sigma-Aldrich) salt via mixing equimolar amounts of both reagents in methanol:water mixture (2:1). Resulting precipitate was then filtrated and recrystallized from acetone. The following compounds of diamines and di- or tri-acid chlorides were used for the synthesis of polyamide materials: p-phenylenediamine (PPD, 98%, Sigma – Aldrich), 1,6 – diaminohexane (1,6-DAH, ≥99,5%, Acros Organics), 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride (1,3,5,BTCTCl, for analysis, Apollo Scientific), terephthaloyl chloride (TCl, ≥99%, Sigma – Aldrich), and adipoyl chloride (AC, 98%, Alfa Aesar). A quaternary amine - tetramethylammonium chloride (TMACl, >98%, Acros Organics) was used to test molecular sieving properties of polyamide modified microITIES. The fused silica capillary tubing having the internal diameter equal to 25 μm was purchased from VWR.

2.2. Electrochemical experiments

Figure 1. Scheme showing classical voltammetric cell (I) used for macroITIES polarization and modification, (II) used for microITIES modification and electroanalytical characterization. The organic phase is marked in yellow, whereas the aqueous phase is marked in blue. Set of electrodes being in contact with the organic phase are marked in red, and for the water phase in black. $RE_{aq/org} = Ag/AgCl$ wire, $CE_{aq/org} =$ platinum electrode (Pt). The third part of figure (III) shows the preparation protocol of the microITIES based system by embedding (A) a silica capillary in a micropipette tip, (B) removing excess capillary using a ceramic knife, and (C) filling the created system with the organic phase followed by a set of electrodes placement.

Electrochemical studies were carried out on macroscopic and microscopic scale. In macroscopic scale (see Fig.1-(I)) a classical voltammetric glass cell (interface radii equal to 0.7 cm) equipped with a set of four electrodes was used. Two Ag/AgCl reference electrodes and two Pt counter electrodes were involved. In microscopic scale (Fig. 1-(II)), the ITIES was supported with a micropipette tip finished with the silica capillary tubing having a diameter equal to around 25 μm . The created microtip was filled with the organic phase and immersed in the aqueous phase. Here, the platinum, and the Ag/AgCl electrodes were used as the aqueous phase counter and reference electrodes, respectively. The platinum wire electrode contacted with the organic phase served as both: the organic phase counter and reference electrode. MicroITIES support was fabricated following procedure reported elsewhere.[22] All experiments were conducted using Autolab 108 (Metrohm®) with Nova 1.11 software.

2.3.SEM - EDX

The scanning electron microscopy (SEM, a Phenom G2 Pure, FEI Company, the Netherlands) was used to examine the morphology of polyamide material formed at the macroscopic and microscopic LLI. SEM images were acquired using a high sensitivity backscatter electron detector (BSD) with an accelerating voltage of 5 kV.

SEM - EDX was also used for local analysis and mapping of manufactured polyamide materials using the JEOL JMS-IT500HR microscope (JEOL, Japan) equipped with the Ultim Max 170 EDS detector (Oxford Instruments, UK).

2.4.Raman Spectroscopy

Raman spectra have been taken with a Renishaw Qontor set-up equipped with a Peletier cooled CCD camera, a laser of 785 nm wavelength working at 50 mW and an edge filter to separate the Rayleigh from the Raman scattered light. A grating with 1200 grooves/mm was used, leading to a spectral resolution of 1 cm^{-1} . The laser light was focused on the microscope stage using a X50 objective with long working distance (11 mm) and a numerical aperture of 0.75. Typical experiments required an average of 4 acquisitions with 5 s of integration time on the detector.

3. Result and discussion

3.1 Polyamides synthesis at macroscopic polarized liquid-liquid interface

We have studied the possibility to assist electrochemically the synthesis of polyamides at the macroscopic ITIES. The possible reaction routes between the various monomers dissolved in either aqueous or the organic phase that we have studied are shown in Fig. 2. The polyamides synthesised are derived from the reaction between one out of two employed diamines and one out of three selected di- or tri-acyl chlorides. As shown in Fig. 2, the investigated pair of monomers are (aq stands for the aqueous phase; org stands for the organic phase): **I** - *p*-phenylenediamine (aq) and 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride (org), **II** - *p*-phenylenediamine (aq) and terephthaloyl chloride (org), **III** - *p*-phenylenediamine (aq) and adipoyl chloride (org), **IV** - 1,6-diaminohexane (aq) and 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride (org), **V** - 1,6-diaminohexane (aq) and terephthaloyl chloride (org). The numbering **I-V** is adopted and refer to resulting polyamides in all section of this manuscript. The interfacial polycondensation of nylon-6,6 (**VI**; reaction between 1,6-diaminohexane and adipoyl chloride) is purposely not marked as it was investigated previously by our group (see [9]).

For *p*-phenylenediamine and 1,6-diaminohexane we have plotted concentration distribution diagrams (Fig. S1). *p*-phenylenediamine pK_a 's values are $pK_{a1} = 2.8$ and $pK_{a2} = 6.2$ [36]. For 1,6-diaminohexane, these values are $pK_{a1} = 10.8$ and $pK_{a2} = 11.9$ [9]. Both monomers soluble in the aqueous phase, have two amine groups located at the periphery of the aromatic ring or alkyl chain. As such, for each diamine, we can distinguish three possible species that may exist in the aqueous phase depending on its pH: this is neutral diamine (A^0); monoprotinated diamine (A^+) or diprotinated diamine (A^{2+}). To form a amide bond, a fraction of compounds providing amine groups with a lone pair of electrons need to be available to attack carbon atom (with a net positive charge). A fraction of protonated amine groups, which are deprived from a lone electron pair, will provide the interfacial electrochemical activity of the amine monomers. In other words, we need charged species that may undergo electrochemically controlled ion transfer from the aqueous to the organic phase being reservoir of the monomers equipped with acyl chloride functionalities. The inspection of the concentration distribution diagrams revealed that the optimal aqueous phase pH for the electrochemically assisted interfacial polycondensation reaction is pH = 6.2 for the *p*-phenylenediamine pH = 11.3 for the 1,6-diaminohexane. Further information taken from the

concentration fraction diagrams indicates that at pH = 6.2 (*p*-phenylenediamine; Fig. S1A) the aqueous phase contains 50% of A⁰; 50% of A⁺; and 0% of A²⁺. For 1,6-diaminohexane we have selected the aqueous phase pH = 11.3 (see Fig. S1B) that fixed its composition to 64% of A⁺; 18% of A²⁺, and 18% of A⁰. The reason why the pH of the aqueous phase solution of the 1,6-diaminohexane was not elevated (lowered fraction of the doubly protonated species – A²⁺) is related to OH⁻ concentration, which when too high could limit the available potential window during voltammetric scanning used for the ITIES modification.

With the pH of the aqueous phase fixed, we have designed the experiment to study the effect of the diamine concentration added to the aqueous phase, in the absence of the acyl chloride in the organic phase, on the shape of the cyclic voltammograms. Fig. S2A and Fig. S2B show the resulting current-potential dependencies for *p*-phenylenediamine and 1,6-diaminohexane in the concentration range from 20 μM to 3 mM, respectively. In both cases we have observed that starting from around 20 μM we can distinguish a pair of signals (positive and negative currents) located on the positive potential difference side of the available potential window. As the concentration of diamine increases (> 500 μM) the current intensity at E > 0.6V grows (as expected) and overlaps with the current linked to the transfer of the background electrolyte, which limits the potential window on more positive side (Na⁺ transfer from the aqueous to the organic phase). Our understanding is that, for *p*-phenylenediamine at pH = 6.2, the positive currents are due to A⁺ transfer from the aqueous to the organic phase, whereas for 1,6-diaminohexane at pH = 11.3, the positive current is a mixture of the A⁺ and A²⁺ transfer from the aqueous to the organic phase. By analogy, the negative currents are due to A⁺ or A⁺/A²⁺ back transfer to the aqueous phase. We also found, that all employed acyl chlorides soluble only in the organic phase, this is 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride (Fig. S2C), terephthaloyl chloride (Fig. S2D) and adipoyl chloride (Fig. S2E), at relatively high concentration fixed to 5 mM of each, do not provide any additional current variation within the available potential window. Acyl chloride functional group may react with water to form carboxylic acid groups and hydrochloric acid as a side product. This means that small fraction of monoanionic or dianionic species with hydrolysed carboxylic groups (high pH) may exist within the interfacial region. Nevertheless, the voltammetric insights do not reveal the presence of such compounds.

Fig. 2 further depicts the ion transfer voltammograms recorded in the presence of different pair of diamines and di- or tri-acyl chlorides dissolved in the aqueous and the organic phase, respectively. For all cases I-V (for the numbering refer to Fig. 2A) the concentration of

acyl chloride dissolved in the organic phase was fixed and equal to 5 mM, whereas the concentration of diamine was an experimental variable progressively increasing from 100 μM to 5 mM.

Figure 2. Left upper corner: Scheme displaying all possible reactions between acyl chlorides and di-amines studied at the ITIES. The numbers of reaction routes from I to V refer to the corresponding cyclic voltammograms recorded during the electrochemically assisted polyamides deposition at the macroscopic ITIES. Concentration of acyl chloride was fixed (5 mM), whereas the concentration of di-amine dissolved in the aqueous phase was increased from 100 to 5000 μM . The photos on the right from cyclic voltammograms are recorded after the interfacial polycondensation reaction occurred. The image (A) shows the polyamide material formed at the ITIES. In the second picture (B), the material is pulled from the interface using a counter electrode from the organic phase.

From Fig. 2 we can notice that reactions I, II, III and IV provide similar features, this is, as the concentration of *p*-phenylenediamine (I, II and II) and 1,6-diaminohexane (IV) increase we can observe the increase in the positive current limiting the potential window on the more positive potential difference side of the cyclic voltammogram. Also, we have noticed additional pair of

peaks located between +0.2V and +0.5V (especially visible in Fig. 2-I, $E_{1/2}$ around 0.41V) for *p*-phenylenediamine and between +0.5V and +0.8V (see Fig. 2-IV, $E_{1/2}$ around 0.58V) for 1,6-diaminohexane. In the presence of the aqueous and the organic phase monomers, a number of electrochemical and chemical reactions can occur: (i) the electrochemically controlled transfer of either A^+ or A^{2+} from the aqueous to the organic phase giving positive current; (ii) reaction of the nitrogen atom having a lone pair of electrons with the carbon atom of the acyl chloride functionality occurring either at the ITIES or on the organic phase side of the ITIES after A^+ transfer or A^0 partitioning to the interfacial region; (iii) the A^+ or A^{2+} dissociation in the organic phase followed by the ion transfer reaction providing new amine groups for the reaction with acyl chloride; (iv) acidification of the aqueous phase side of the ITIES as the interfacial polycondensation proceeds (release of protons) that may affect the distribution of $A^0/A^+/A^{2+}$ further affecting the shape of the cyclic voltammograms; and finally, (v) the formation of charged dimers/trimers that may transfer back from the organic phase to the aqueous phase. As a matter of fact, for the latter, we believe that the extra pair of signals recorded before the prominent limiting current obtained for the higher diamine concentration originates from these complex species transfer. This is in line with the prediction, as the formed amides (dimers, trimers) should be more hydrophobic as compared with the charged diamine species shifting their ion transfer potentials to less positive potential difference values. Reaction between 1,6-diaminohexane and terephthaloyl chloride (V) gave rise to initially increasing signals attributed to the amine transfer from the aqueous to the organic phase (up to 100 μ M), followed by a visible current drop, even these attributed to the transfer of the aqueous phase background electrolyte ions. This is especially visible on the cyclic voltammogram from Fig. 2-V, marked with a black solid line and attributed to the 5 mM 1,6-diaminohexane and 5 mM terephthaloyl chloride. The intensity of the peak current located at $E = +0.05$ V is nearly unaffected after addition of 100 μ M of 1,6-diaminohexane and drops by around 85% when final concentration of diamine equal to 5 mM is present in the aqueous phase. This clearly demonstrates that the permeability of the formed polyphthalamide terephthaloyl/1,6-diaminohexane film is low, and hence, should display efficient ionic sieving properties. Each pair of monomers, after excessive cycling (>20 cycles) resulted in the formation of the deposit at the ITIES. Visual inspection of the formed polymeric films is additionally depicted on the photos taken for the cell after voltammetric cyclic (see Fig. 2, photos on the right from the cyclic voltammograms). First photo was taken for the cell with the intact ITIES whereas the second shows the film after lifting the

organic phase counter electrode. By doing this, we observed that compact and relatively thick films were obtained via reaction route I and IV (reaction between 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride and *p*-phenylenediamine or 1,6-diaminohexane, respectively). In both cases, the film could be lifted from the ITIES after the voltammetric deposition. Most probably, formed polyamide films hold a relatively open and cross linked structure originating from the existence of three acyl chloride substituents in 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride monomer, which do not inhibit the mass transfer of diamine from the aqueous to the organic phase. This is in line with the increasing ionic currents growing along with the increasing aqueous phase monomer concentration. For the reaction route II and III we have obtained films that were breaking easily once the organic phase counter electrode was moved. Similar features were attributed to the reaction route V, which displayed significant blocking effect on the transfer of all ions present in the cell (see Fig. 2-V). The fragile polyamide film could be easily disrupted, most probably meaning that this thin film is not permeable to either of the monomers already at the initial deposition time.

Fig. 3 shows the data obtained for the polyamide materials extracted from the macroscopic ITIES after electrochemically assisted deposition process. With scanning electron microscopy, we have noticed that different polyamides, as expected, exhibit different surface morphologies.

Figure 3. SEM images recorded for polyamide films synthesized and collected from the ITIES. **A-I** – *p*-phenylenediamine and 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride, **B-II** – *p*-phenylenediamine and terephthaloyl chloride, **C-III** – *p*-phenylenediamine and adipoyl chloride, **D-IV** – 1,6-diaminohexane and 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride, **E-V** – 1,6-diaminohexane and terephthaloyl chloride, **F-VI** – 1,6-diaminohexane and adipoyl chloride. **G-IV** and **H-V** are the Raman spectra recorded for polyamides derived from a reaction between 1,6-diaminohexane and 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride; and 1,6-diaminohexane and terephthaloyl chloride, respectively. 50% red laser (785nm) intensity was used.

The inspection of the SEM images reveals that polyamides formed via route I, II and III are rather spongy with the debris existing at the material surface whereas the remaining polymers obtained in reaction IV, V and VI display significantly less fine features. Fig. S3 available in the electronic supporting information provide more SEM images recorded at three different magnifications. All collected materials were also examined using Raman spectroscopy. Obtained spectra are not identical to the spectra already reported in the literature for e.g. polyamide-6,6 or polyaramid fibres like Kevlar.[37–41] The results obtained using Raman spectroscopy were similar for all interfacially formed deposits and most probably correspond to the background electrolyte which apparently is entrapped in the film upon interfacial synthesis (the recorded Raman spectra for BTTPACl – data not shown – is very similar to the spectra depicted in Fig. 3G and Fig. 3H). . EDX analysis has shown that in addition to carbon, nitrogen, and oxygen polymeric films contain other elements at non negligible % contribution. We have found sodium, phosphate, and chloride indicating that the background electrolyte salts (from both phases) may be entrapped within the polyamide material during the interfacial polycondensation process. We have found that on average, more background electrolyte ions are present in the polyamides derived from reactions IV, V and VI (e.g. up to 11.20% of Na⁺ found in film IV). Also, we have compared the %composition of C, N and O in the films formed at the ITIES with the expected (theoretical) %composition of the pure films. Obtained correlation holds expected order of magnitude (see Table 1).

Table 1. %Composition of the polyamide films collected from the ITIES. **I** – *p*-phenylenediamine + 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride, **II** – *p*-phenylenediamine + terephthaloyl chloride, **III** – *p*-phenylenediamine + adipoyl chloride, **IV** – 1,6-diaminohexane + 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride, **V** – 1,6-diaminohexane + terephthaloyl chloride, **VI** – 1,6-diaminohexane + adipoyl chloride.

TESTED COMPOSITION

NAME ELEMENT [%]	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
C	66	73	71	66	73	65
N	4	12	10	4	6	7
O	10	11	15	9	13	16
Na	9	0	1	11	4	7
P	2	0	1	0	1	2
Cl	9	4	2	10	3	3

THEORETICAL COMPOSITION

NAME ELEMENT [%]	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
C	68	71	66	61	68	64
N	15	12	13	10	11	12
O	13	13	15	17	13	14

3.2. Microscopic liquid-liquid interface modified with different polyamides

Figure 4. Experimental sequence aiming at (A) bare microITIES characterization; (B) microITIES modification with the chosen polyamide (example shows the reaction between *p*-phenylenediamine (aq) and 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride (org) and (C) modified microITIES characterization with quaternary ammonium cations.

In order to test polyamides compactness formed at the ITIES the entire system was miniaturized using fused silica capillaries serving as the soft junction supports. **Fig. 4** shows the typical processing route applied for all studied polyamides. The **1st step (A)** accounts for the microITIES preparation (see procedure reported elsewhere [22]) and the resulting supports electroanalytical evaluation with the cyclic voltammetry in the presence of the model ion. The currents originating from the tetramethylammonium (TMA^+) cation transfer from the aqueous to the organic phase were used to calculate the diameter of the supported ITIES [42]. As it will be shown for all voltammograms displayed below, the mass transfer of TMA^+ from the aqueous to the organic phase follows the hemispherical diffusion layer profile providing sigmoidal current response. The back transfer happening inside the capillary is limited by the linear diffusion, and hence, the negative, peak like signal is recorded. Only the tips having $24.5 \mu\text{m} \pm 1.0 \mu\text{m}$ were used for further processing. **Fig. 4B** shows the electrochemically assisted microITIES modification step. The concentration of monomers was set to 10 mM and 5 mM for

diamine and di-/tri-acyl chloride dissolved in the aqueous and the organic phase, respectively. For given concentrations we were obtaining enough material for further analysis, and we also found that these concentration provided films affecting the interfacial charge transfer reactions. The interfacial polycondensation was assisted by cyclic voltammetry with the experiential variable being the number of recorded voltammetric cycles: 5, 10, 15 or 20. In the last step (**Fig. 4C**), the microITIES modified with polyamide film with the predefined number of voltammetric cycles was removed from the aqueous phase containing diamine. The tip was rinsed with demineralized H₂O and was further inserted into a fresh cell to which the quaternary ammonium model ion (TMA⁺) was added. The outcome of the molecular sieving properties for each formed polyamide film are presented and discussed below.

(I) *p*-phenylenediamine and 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride

First, we have investigated the polyamide (I) created using *p*-phenylenediamine and 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride. **Fig. 5A and 5B** shows the monomer structures used during electrochemically assisted interfacial polycondensation. Before ITIES modification the composition of both phases was set to: the aqueous phase - 10 mM *p*-phenylenediamine dissolved in a 10mM BRB at pH = 6.2; the organic phase – 5 mM 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride dissolved in a 5 mM BTPPA⁺TPBCL in 1,2-DCE. As shown in Fig. 5C, formed material covers a surface being slightly greater than the surface of the pore (around 25 μm in diameter) indicating that: (i) the material grows towards the aqueous phase side of the ITIES as the reaction time pass by; or (ii) the drop in the ITIES interfacial tension caused by the adsorbing dimers/trimers/oligomers affects the position of the soft junction going into the aqueous phase during the electrochemically assisted modification. In Fig. 5D or Fig. S5 one can notice that obtained film is not homogenous. Analysis of the image suggests that the formed polyamide holds surface heterogeneity which is difficult to assess with SEM analysis. **Fig. 5E – 5H** are the cyclic voltammograms recorded in the absence and in the presence of TMA⁺ (in the aqueous phase) at the ITIES modified with polyamide (I) after indicated number of voltammetric cycles. We have observed that in the absence of the TMA⁺ in the aqueous phase, the positive and the negative limiting currents are becoming more resistive for the longer deposition process, although still being permeable for Na⁺ ions (more positive potential difference side of the potential window) and the aqueous phase background electrolyte anions (Cl⁻, phosphate, borate or CH₃COO⁻; more negative side of the potential window). The inspection of the positive

currents (sigmoidal wave corresponding to the transfer of the TMA⁺ from the aqueous to the organic phase) reveals that up to 10 cycles the signal intensity for 180 μM TMA⁺ remains rather unaffected, after 15 cycles it drops by around 93%, whereas after 20 cycles the signal is missing. This suggests that the film compactness do not allow for the TMA⁺ transfer or its thickness affects the TMA⁺ diffusivity across the modified ITIES.

Figure 5. The figure shows structural formulas of *p*-phenylenediamine and 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride dissolved in the aqueous (A) and the organic (B) phase, respectively. C and D shows SEM micrographics taken for the polyamide modified microITIES formed after 20 consecutively recorded voltammetric scans. E, F, G and H are the voltammograms recorded at modified microITIES in the presence of [TMA⁺] = 60 or 180 μM after different amounts of voltammetric cycle recorded during polyamide film formation at the ITIES. The recorded blank reading corresponds to the bold cyclic voltammogram recorded at modified microITIES in the absence of TMA⁺.

(II) *p*-phenylenediamine and terephthaloyl chloride

The same characterization procedure was applied to all studied pairs of monomers. Analogical set of data for polyamide (II) is depicted in Fig. 6 and Fig. S5-II. SEM micrographies indicate the formed film entirely covers the pore. The morphology of the interfacial formed material is distinct from the polyamide (I) as not clear pinholes and holes are visible at its surface. Also, from Fig. S5-II (the SEM image recorded for the highest magnification) one can notice a clear boundary between the film and the edge of the pore, which indicates that the film formation

occurs within the capillary ingress. With the exception of the sigmoidal wave intensity attributed to 180 μM TMA⁺ for the film formed with 5 voltammetric scans, we have observed that the polyamide (II) decreases the sigmoidal wave positive current 0.90 nA for 10 cycles, 0.56 nA for 15 cycles, and 0.16 nA for 20 cycles.

Figure 6. The figure shows structural formulas of *p*-phenylenediamine and terephthaloyl chloride dissolved in the aqueous (A) and the organic (B) phase, respectively. C and D shows SEM micrographics taken for the polyamide modified microITIES formed after 20 consecutively recorded voltammetric scans. E, F, G and H are the cyclic voltammograms recorded at modified microITIES in the absence (blank) and in the presence of [TMA⁺] = 60 or 180 μM after indicated amount of the consecutively applied cycles. The recorded blank reading corresponds to the bold cyclic voltammogram recorded at modified microITIES in the absence of TMA⁺.

(III) *p*-phenylenediamine and adipoyl chloride

The polyamide (III) gave a material with very interesting surface properties. SEM images from Fig. 7C and 7D clearly indicate that the film surface packed with a number of black spots which we have attributed to the film intrinsic porosity. Similar to other capillaries the film was formed within the pore and was slightly covering its edges. The biggest pores of the polyamide (III) are having up to a few hundred of nanometres (see Fig. S5-III; SEM micrographie recorded at highest magnification), and hence, our expectation was that the film will be permeable to TMA⁺. Our prediction was confirmed with the voltammetric data shown in Fig. 7E – 7H. As a material with a pore size being a few order of magnitude larger than the hydrodynamic radius of the

TMA⁺, the drop of the positive ionic current attributed to the studied model ion was equal to around 20% when comparing the film formed with 5 and 20 voltammetric cycles.

Figure 7. The figure shows structural formulas of *p*-phenylenediamine and adipoyl chloride dissolved in the aqueous (A) and the organic (B) phase, respectively. C and D shows SEM micrographics taken for the polyamide modified microITIES formed after 20 consecutively recorded voltammetric scans. E, F, G and H are the voltammograms recorded at modified microITIES in the presence of [TMA⁺] = 60 or 180 μM after different amounts of voltammetric cycles recorded during polyamide formation at the ITIES. The recorded blank reading corresponds to the bold cyclic voltammogram recorded at modified microITIES in the absence of TMA⁺.

The third pair of monomers to synthesis of polyamide material were *p*-phenylenediamine and adipoyl chloride. **Figure 7** shows the monomer structures used for the synthesis reaction, voltammograms recorded for the modified microITIES systems for a given number of scanning cycles and selected SEM images for x1000 and x5000 magnification. The remaining images recorded using SEM were placed in supporting information (**SI Fig. S5**). The 10mM *P*-phenylenediamine was in a 10mM BRB at pH=6.2 and 5mM adipoyl chloride was in a 5mM BTPPA⁺Cl⁻ in 1,2-dichloroethane. The visible blank in the graph shows the voltammogram recorded for the modified microITIES system. Polyamide is formed at the miniaturized liquid – liquid interface in an electrochemically controlled manner, but it is very brittle and the model ion easily passes through it. A decrease in the signal of the model ion transition from the

aqueous phase to the organic phase and back is visible, but it was not possible to obtain an effectively blocked interface with the polyamide material.

(IV) 1,6-diaminohexane and 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride

Figure 8. The figure shows structural formulas of 1,6-diaminohexane and 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride dissolved in the aqueous (A) and the organic (B) phase, respectively. C and D shows SEM micrographics taken for the polyamide modified microITIES formed after 20 consecutively recorded voltammetric scans. E, F, G and H are the voltammograms recorded at modified microITIES in the absence and in the presence of [TMA⁺] = 60 or 180 μM after different number of applied voltammetric cycles. The recorded blank reading corresponds to the bold cyclic voltammogram recorded at modified microITIES in the absence of TMA⁺.

The 4th pair of tested monomers (1,6-diaminohexane and 1,3,5-benzenetricarbonyl trichloride) gave a set of data depicted in **Fig. 8**. SEM images from Fig. 8C and 8D (also **Fig. S5-IV**) indicate that: (i) the film is compact; (ii) wrinkles exist at the surface and probably are the artefact of the drying process, and (iii) the surrounding of the capillary pore is decorated with fibrous features which suggests that some fibres may grow on the aqueous phase side during interfacial polycondensation, and further collapse and remain at the surface of the capillary as the polyamide is dried. Interestingly, polyamide (IV) started to become an obstacle for the TMA⁺ transfer either from the aqueous to the organic or from the organic to the aqueous phase

already after first five deposition cycles (see Fig. 8E). MicroITIES modified with polyamide (IV) with five deposition cycles gave additional voltammetric features located within less positive potential difference side (see positive peak signal at around +0.2V), that we think can be attributed to the anionic species (being the aqueous phase background electrolyte) transfer from the organic (inside of the capillary, where the mass transfer is governed by the linear diffusion) to the aqueous phase. Further increase in the number of deposition cycles blocked the interface, and even triggered the electrochemical instability manifested by the irregular current patterns as shown in Fig. 8F and Fig. 8G. The film formed after 20 modification cycles was entirely impermeable for the TMA⁺ transfer.

(V) 1,6-diaminohexane and terephthaloyl chloride

Figure 9. The figure shows structural formulas of 1,6-diaminohexane and terephthaloyl chloride dissolved in the aqueous (A) and the organic (B) phase, respectively. C and D shows SEM micrographics taken for the polyamide modified microITIES formed after 20 consecutively recorded voltammetric scans. E, F, G and H are the voltammograms recorded at modified microITIES in the absence and in the presence of [TMA⁺] = 60 or 180 μM after different number of applied voltammetric cycles. The recorded blank reading corresponds to the bold cyclic voltammogram recorded at modified microITIES in the absence of TMA⁺.

The last studied deposit was derived from a reaction between 1,6-diaminohexane and terephthaloyl chloride. SEM images from Fig. 9C, 9D and Fig. S5-V are in line with the observations we have made when performing the experiments at the macroscopic ITIES. The

formed film covers only part of the micropore, which suggest its high fragility. The film formed at the macroscopic ITIES could not be lifted with the organic phase counter electrode as it was breaking and remaining as a broken flakes within soft junction. Fig. 9D shows that film covers only part of the pore ingress and probably has broken when both phases were removed from the film neighbourhood. The very high compactness of the film was already visible during the macroITIES modification process as the ionic currents originating from the 1,6-diaminohexane transfer were dropping as the film thickness was increasing. MicroITIES modified with polyamide (V) with 5 voltammetric cycles gave a curves with potential window elongated at the more negative potential difference side (anionic species transfer blocking effect) and blocked transfer of the TMA⁺ from the aqueous to the organic phase (significantly reduced positive current signals). Also, the signal of the TMA⁺ back transfer was shifted towards negative potential difference values indicating that additional portion of the energy must be supplied to the system to cross the ITIES modified with polyamide (V). Fig. 9F, 9G and 9H shows that the microITIES is not permeable to any ions present in both phases indicating that the ITIES is entirely blocked by the interfacially formed material.

Based on our screening study, we have concluded that in all cases the polyamide deposits were formed within the capillary ingress. For most deposits (I – IV) it was obvious that the reaction proceeds over time as the formed polymeric material could be found at the pore surroundings. In case of reaction (V) the film was found to be thin and located only within the pore, which further suggests that the compactness of the deposited polymer self-inhibited its further growth. Finally, the interfacially formed polyamides can be attributed to three classes of materials: (i) deposits with pores being significantly bigger than the size of the employed model ions – reaction - III; (ii) deposits that display a sieving effect – reaction I, II and IV; and (iii) deposit that entirely block the liquid-liquid interface – reaction V.

4. Conclusions

In this work, we have used the voltammetry to study and assist the interfacial polycondensation of a number of polyamides formed at the electrified liquid-liquid interface. Optimized soft junction modification conditions were chosen to form polymeric materials derived from reactions between aqueous phase soluble 1,6-diaminohexane or *p*-phenylenediamine and acyl chlorides dissolved in the organic phase, this is 1,3,5-

benzenetricarbonyl trichloride, terephthaloyl chloride or adipoyl chloride. Formed materials were characterized using SEM, EDX and Raman Spectroscopy. Next, the microscopic liquid-liquid interface supported with a fused silica capillary was modified with all studied polyamide materials and the resulting platforms were characterized in terms of their molecular sieving properties. The effect of the deposition conditions on the ionic currents being attributed to the tetramethylammonium cation interfacial transfer were investigated. We have found that the polyamide formed as a result of the reaction between *p*-phenylenediamine and adipoyl chloride gave a porous deposit being permeable even when longer deposition times (number of applied voltammetric deposition cycles) were applied. The film formed using 1,6-diaminohexane and terephthaloyl chloride entirely blocked the interface, whereas for the other pairs the model ion (tetramethylammonium cation) transfer was inhibited only for thicker films, still being permeable to the background electrolyte ions. We believe, that proposed platform can be used as the model system for the evolution of the polymeric films derived from the interfacial polycondensation reactions.

5. Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

6. Acknowledgements

The presented research was financed by the National Science Centre Poland as part of the PRELUDIUM 19 project (UMO-2020/37/N/ST4/00270). The authors are also grateful to Polish National Agency For Academic Exchange and Campus France for financing PHC Polonium Project (BPN/BFR/2021/1/00006).

7. References

- [1] K. Marchildon, Polyamides - Still strong after seventy years, *Macromol. React. Eng.* 5 (2011) 22–54. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mren.201000017>.
- [2] J.A. Reglero Ruiz, M. Trigo-López, F.C. García, J.M. García, Functional aromatic polyamides, *Polymers (Basel)*. 9 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym9090414>.

- [3] L. Shen, R. Cheng, M. Yi, W.S. Hung, S. Japip, L. Tian, X. Zhang, S. Jiang, S. Li, Y. Wang, Polyamide-based membranes with structural homogeneity for ultrafast molecular sieving, *Nat. Commun.* 13 (2022) 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-28183-1>.
- [4] Y. Wen, H. Chen, X. Zhou, Q. Deng, C. Zhao, X. Gong, A polyamide resin based method for adsorption of anthocyanins from blackberries, *New J. Chem.* 40 (2016) 3773–3780. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c6nj00054a>.
- [5] X. Zhang, W. Fan, T. Liu, Fused deposition modeling 3D printing of polyamide-based composites and its applications, *Compos. Commun.* 21 (2020) 100413. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coco.2020.100413>.
- [6] K. Piradashvili, E.M. Alexandrino, F.R. Wurm, K. Landfester, Reactions and polymerizations at the liquid-liquid interface, *Chem. Rev.* 116 (2016) 2141–2169. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.5b00567>.
- [7] E.L. Wittbecker, P.W. Morgan, Interfacial polycondensation. I., *J. Polym. Sci. Part A Polym. Chem.* 34 (1996) 521–529. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pola.1996.815>.
- [8] K. Kowalewska, Nylon Rope Trick, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=S6asCwVG8zU&t=14s>. (2020). <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=S6asCwVG8zU>.
- [9] K. Kowalewska, K. Sipa, A. Leniart, S. Skrzypek, L. Poltorak, Electrochemistry at the liquid–liquid interface rediscovers interfacial polycondensation of nylon-6,6, *Electrochem. Commun.* 115 (2020) 106732. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.elecom.2020.106732>.
- [10] D. Fermi, H.J. Lee, H.H. Girault, Electrochemistry at liquid/liquid interfaces: methodology and potential applications, *Electrochim. Acta.* 45 (2000) 2647–2662. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0013-4686\(00\)00343-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0013-4686(00)00343-1).
- [11] Petr Vanysek and Luis Basaez Ramirez, Interface Between Two Immiscible Liquid Electrolytes: A Review, *J. Chil. Chem. Soc.* 2 (2008) 1455–1464. <https://doi.org/10.4067/S0717-97072008000200002>.
- [12] A. Gamero-Quijano, J.A. Manzanares, S.M.B.H. Ghazvini, P.J. Low, M.D. Scanlon, Potential-Modulated Ion Distributions in the Back-to-Back Electrical Double Layers at a

- Polarised Liquid|Liquid Interface Regulate the Kinetics of Interfacial Electron Transfer, *ChemElectroChem*. 202201042 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1002/celc.202201042>.
- [13] J. Strutwolf, M.D. Scanlon, D.W.M. Arrigan, Electrochemical ion transfer across liquid/liquid interfaces confined within solid-state micropore arrays - Simulations and experiments, *Analyst*. 134 (2009) 148–158. <https://doi.org/10.1039/b815256j>.
- [14] R. Chen, K. Xu, M. Shen, Avocado oil, coconut oil, walnut oil as true oil phase for ion transfer at nanoscale liquid/liquid interfaces, *Electrochim. Acta*. 357 (2020) 136788. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2020.136788>.
- [15] Z. Samec, Electrochemistry at the interface between two immiscible electrolyte solutions (IUPAC technical report), *Pure Appl. Chem*. 76 (2004) 2147–2180. <https://doi.org/10.1351/pac200476122147>.
- [16] S. Amemiya, Y. Kim, R. Ishimatsu, B. Kabagambe, Electrochemical heparin sensing at liquid/liquid interfaces and polymeric membranes, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem*. 399 (2011) 571–579. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-010-4056-2>.
- [17] R. Zazpe, C. Hibert, J. O'Brien, Y.H.Y.H. Lanyon, D.W.M.M.D.W.M. Arrigan, Ion-transfer voltammetry at silicon membrane-based arrays of micro-liquid-liquid interfaces, *Lab Chip*. 7 (2007) 1732–1737. <https://doi.org/10.1039/b712601h>.
- [18] R. Ishimatsu, J. Kim, P. Jing, C.C. Striemer, D.Z. Fang, P.M. Fauchet, J.L. McGrath, S. Amemiya, Ion-selective permeability of an ultrathin nanoporous silicon membrane as probed by scanning electrochemical microscopy using micropipet-supported ITIES tips., *Anal. Chem*. 82 (2010) 7127–34. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac1005052>.
- [19] P. Borgul, K. Rudnicki, L. Chu, A. Leniart, S. Skrzypek, E.J.R. Sudhölter, L. Poltorak, Layer-by-layer (LbL) assembly of polyelectrolytes at the surface of a fiberglass membrane used as a support of the polarized liquid–liquid interface, *Electrochim. Acta*. 363 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2020.137215>.
- [20] S. Liu, Q. Li, Y. Shao, Electrochemistry at micro- and nanoscopic liquid/liquid interfaces, *Chem. Soc. Rev*. 40 (2011) 2236–2253. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c0cs00168f>.
- [21] H. Hu, S. Xie, X. Meng, P. Jing, M. Zhang, L. Shen, Z. Zhu, M. Li, Q. Zhuang, Y. Shao,

- Fabrication and characterization of submicrometer- and nanometer-sized double-barrel pipets, *Anal. Chem.* 78 (2006) 7034–7039. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac060773r>.
- [22] K. Rudnicki, L. Poltorak, S. Skrzypek, E.J.R. Sudhölter, Fused silica micro-capillaries used for a simple miniaturization of the electrified liquid – liquid interface, *Anal. Chem.* 90 (2018) 7112–7116. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.8b01351>.
- [23] L. Poltorak, A. Gamero-quijano, G. Herzog, A. Walcarius, Decorating soft electrified interfaces : From molecular assemblies to nano-objects, *Appl. Mater. Today.* 9 (2017) 533–550. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmt.2017.10.001>.
- [24] M.C. Collins, M. Hébrant, G. Herzog, Ion transfer at polarised liquid-liquid interfaces modified with adsorbed silica nanoparticles, *Electrochim. Acta.* 282 (2018) 155–162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2018.06.036>.
- [25] K. Kowalewska, K. Sipa, K. Kaczmarek, S. Skrzypek, L. Poltorak, Interfacial Synthesis of Nylon-6,6 and Its Modification with Silver-Based Nanoparticles at the Electrified Liquid-Liquid Interface, *ChemElectroChem.* 9 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1002/celec.202200435>.
- [26] N. Younan, M. Hojeij, L. Ribeaucourt, H.H. Girault, Electrochemical properties of gold nanoparticles assembly at polarised liquid|liquid interfaces, *Electrochem. Commun.* 12 (2010) 912–915. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.elecom.2010.04.019>.
- [27] M.D. Scanlon, E. Smirnov, T.J. Stockmann, P. Peljo, Gold Nanofilms at Liquid-Liquid Interfaces: An Emerging Platform for Redox Electrocatalysis, Nanoplasmonic Sensors, and Electrovariable Optics, *Chem. Rev.* 118 (2018) 3722–3751. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.7b00595>.
- [28] A.N.J. Rodgers, S.G. Booth, R.A.W. Dryfe, Particle deposition and catalysis at the interface between two immiscible electrolyte solutions (ITIES): A mini-review, *Electrochem. Commun.* 47 (2014) 17–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.elecom.2014.07.009>.
- [29] M. Platt, R.A.W. Dryfe, E.P.L. Roberts, Electrodeposition of palladium nanoparticles at the liquid-liquid interface using porous alumina templates, *Electrochim. Acta.* 48 (2003) 3037–3046. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0013-4686\(03\)00373-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0013-4686(03)00373-6).
- [30] E. Smirnov, P. Peljo, M.D. Scanlon, H.H. Girault, Gold Nanofilm Redox Catalysis for

- Oxygen Reduction at Soft Interfaces, *Electrochim. Acta.* 197 (2016) 362–373. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2015.10.104>.
- [31] A. Uehara, S.G. Booth, S.Y. Chang, S.L.M. Schroeder, T. Imai, T. Hashimoto, J.F.W. Mosselmanns, R.A.W. Dryfe, Electrochemical Insight into the Brust-Schiffrin Synthesis of Au Nanoparticles, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 137 (2015) 15135–15144. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.5b07825>.
- [32] V.J. Cunnane, U. Evans, Formation of oligomers of methyl- and phenyl-pyrrole at an electrified liquid/liquid interface, *Chem. Commun.* (1998) 2163–2164. <https://doi.org/10.1039/a806365f>.
- [33] K. Gorgy, F. Fusalba, U. Evans, K. Kontturi, V.J. Cunnane, Electropolymerization of 2,2':5',2" terthiophene at an electrified liquid-liquid interface, *Synth. Met.* 125 (2001) 365–373. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0379-6779\(01\)00474-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0379-6779(01)00474-X).
- [34] M.F. Suárez-Herrera, A. Gamero-Quijano, M.D. Scanlon, Electrosynthesis of poly(2,5-dimercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazole) films and their composites with gold nanoparticles at a polarised liquid|liquid interface, *Electrochim. Acta.* 424 (2022) 140677. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2022.140677>.
- [35] R.A. Lehane, A. Gamero-Quijano, S. Malijauskaite, A. Holzinger, M. Conroy, F. Laffir, A. Kumar, U. Bangert, K. McGourty, M.D. Scanlon, Electrosynthesis of Biocompatible Free-Standing PEDOT Thin Films at a Polarized Liquid|Liquid Interface, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 144 (2022) 4853–4862. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.1c12373>.
- [36] A. Meyer, K. Fischer, Oxidative transformation processes and products of paraphenylenediamine (PPD) and para-toluenediamine (PTD)—a review, *Environ. Sci. Eur.* 27 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-015-0044-7>.
- [37] S.M. Shebanov, I.K. Novikov, A. V. Pavlikov, O.B. Anañin, I.A. Gerasimov, IR and Raman Spectra of Modern Aramid Fibers, *Fibre Chem.* 48 (2016) 158–164. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10692-016-9761-y>.
- [38] J. V. Miller, E.G. Bartick, Forensic analysis of single fibers by Raman spectroscopy, *Appl. Spectrosc.* 55 (2001) 1729–1732. <https://doi.org/10.1366/0003702011954099>.

- [39] N.E. Triggs, J.J. Valentine, Raman Studies of Hydrogen Bonding in Polyamides, *Isr. J. Chem.* 34 (1994) 89–93. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijch.199400013>.
- [40] B.H. Stuart, Polymer crystallinity studied using Raman spectroscopy, *Vib. Spectrosc.* 10 (1996) 79–87. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0924-2031\(95\)00042-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0924-2031(95)00042-9).
- [41] N. Tong, C. Zhu, C. Zhang, Y. Zhang, Study on Raman spectra of aliphatic polyamide fibers, *Optik (Stuttg.)*. 127 (2016) 21–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijleo.2015.09.180>.
- [42] T. Hinoue, E. Ikeda, S. Watariguchi, Y. Kibune, Thermal modulation voltammetry with laser heating at an aqueous|nitrobenzene solution microinterface: Determination of the standard entropy changes of transfer for tetraalkylammonium ions, *Anal. Chem.* 79 (2007) 291–298. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac061315l>.